

K7 Unified Messaging, Free Fax And Voicemail To Email

Forget your phone number or security code?

Click here and have them emailed to you!

Access all your

messages right here

on K7's web site!

Need to discontinue

your K7 service?

Click here.

Learn More About Kall8

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Kall8.com

Q: What is K7 Unified Messaging? back to questions K7 Unified Messaging gives you an independent voicemail box that is not attached to any of your actual phone numbers! (This is also a fax mail box). With K7 Unified Messaging, no one can hear your messages but you, since your messages are not tied to any phone.

Q: What can K7 do for me? back to questions With K7, you can receive faxes and voice messages without having to be at the office. You can receive both faxes and voice messages the same way you receive your email. Your voice messages and fax messages will be sent as email attachments and can be viewed with the click of a mouse. If you can't access your email remotely, you can receive both faxes and voice messages via the K7 Web site. K7 will also work with free email services such as "Hotmail".

Q: Are there any fees for K7? back to questions No. You won't receive a bill from us. K7 does not charge you setup or monthly fees-unlike the local phone company.

Q: What equipment do I need? back to questions You need a web enabled computer (which is likely if you are reading this) and to hear voicemail you also need a sound card, speakers and software such as real player or winamp.

Q: Do I still need a stand-alone fax machine? back to questions Your PC becomes your gateway to receive faxes. Your faxes can be easily received, viewed and printed. There is no need for a second line to receive fax messages. If you use the same line for your computer modem, your fax and phone, with K7 (and "Call Forward Busy") you will never miss a call or fax. You will need a scanner to fax documents, photos, etc. that have not been created on your PC.

Q: Do I have to download software? back to questions Not if you have Windows. Mac and Unix users must download software. Quick Time Pro will open .wav and .tif files. Mac users should check to see if they already have

that version. A good resource for downloading such programs is: Download.com

Q: Can I use K7 to send faxes? back to questions To send faxes directly from your PC we recommend Faxaway email to fax service. There is no per page charge and the per minute charges start at 10 cents a minute. Please visit www.faxaway.com for more information.

Q: How do I make changes to My Account? back to questions You can make changes to your account information by going to My Account. From your account you can view your faxes, listen to voicemail, update your email address, change your password, choose your method of delivery (whether it's via email, the web, or both) and select from the two types of .wav files that change the size and quality of the voice messages you receive. The GSM .wav files are the default file formats you will receive upon sign up and are the smaller, lower quality voice messages than the PCM .wav file (larger and higher quality sound file) that you may also choose upon sign up. You may also change your preference when you login to "My K7". To access your account you will need to enter your K7 number and security code.

Q: How do I check my messages? back to questions You can check for messages two different ways! On the Web: Your messages can be checked on the Web. Log into your own private [send fax online canada](http://www.k7.net) mailbox at www.k7.net. Your messages are stored here and no one else has access. It's also a great way to get messages when you're traveling, since you save on all those long-distance calls. In your email: Another way to get your faxes and voicemail is to have it sent to your email account. Voice messages are in ".wav" format and faxes in ".tif" so no special software is needed to hear or view them. Each message includes the date and time of the call. In the FROM line of your email is the phone number of the caller (provided their ID is not turned off). You will hear the exact message that was left - in the voice of the person who called.

Q: Can I have my home, office phone and fax machine automatically answered by K7? back to questions Yes, you can have all your phone calls and faxes answered by K7. To do this just call your local phone company and order "Call Forward Busy" and "Call Forward No-answer". "Call Forward Busy" will forward calls directly to K7 when your line is busy, and "Call Forward No Answer" will forward a call after a specified number of rings. Another alternative available from your local phone company is "Call Forward Variable". When you know you aren't available, this feature allows you to forward all your calls to K7 on the first ring.

Q: Does my PC need to be "on" to receive faxes by email? back to questions Unlike fax modems, which require your PC to be "on", K7 messages are received at your ISP and are downloaded when you receive your email.

Q: How do I personalize my outgoing message? back to questions Personalize your greeting by calling your K7 number and pressing "*". You will be prompted for your security code and then presented with menu options to change your personal greeting or your security code: Press "1" to change your greeting and press "2" to change your security code. Please note that if you have no greeting you may press "*" during the confirmation message to be prompted for your security code.

Q: How long does it take to receive a fax? back to questions Once K7 receives a fax or voice message, it is immediately sent to your email address and/or saved at K7 for access via a web page, depending on how your K7 account is set up.

Q: How many messages can I have? How long can I keep the old ones? back to questions Your K7 mailbox can hold up to 20 messages at one time. (This includes both voice and fax). That's the total of both new messages and any old messages you have saved. All messages are deleted after 7 days. This is one of the advantages of receiving your messages by email. The only limits are those set by your email provider.

Q: What is the maximum message length? back to questions Your callers may leave a message up to five full minutes in length. You can receive multiple pages in a single fax transmission, but the file cannot exceed 2 megs.

Q: How can K7 Unified Messaging be Free? back to questions The service is paid for by advertisers. Their banners on our Web site. There is no charge for registering, no per page charges, no monthly subscription fees, no catches or gimmicks.

Q: Where is K7 Unified Messaging available? back to questions by using the Web or email options, messages can be checked from practically anywhere. Callers leave you a message by calling a local Seattle phone number. Our parent company, ITL offers 800 service from the U.S., Canada and parts of the Caribbean. For more information go to www.itltd.net.

Q: What about long distance calls? back to questions With the competitive telecommunications market, most long distance carriers charge the same for calling anywhere in the U.S. Competitive long distance rates of five to ten cents per minute means a typical fax will cost around seven cents to send anywhere in the U.S. Rates are based on the senders long distance carrier. K7's parent company, ITL (International Telcom), offers Kallcents a long distance service with a rate of 9.9 cents per minute and no monthly charges or minimums. For additional information, go to www.kallcents.com. Alternatively, you can get a Toll Free 800 number pointed at your K7 Account. Go to Kall8 for details.

Q: I'm having difficulty opening or viewing the .tif fax files. What should I do? back to questions If you are having difficulty opening your .tif fax files online, right click them and select save to disk on the pop up menu. After you have the .tif file saved to disk try opening it with your image viewer. If you need an image viewer for Windows PCs try Tucows for several different .tif viewers.

Q: Can I have a toll free number for my K7 Unified Messaging Service? back to questions Yes, you can. Visit Kall8 for details on getting your own toll free 800 number service.

Q: How do I utilize K7 from outside the USA? back to questions The K7 service center is located in Seattle, Washington. All K7 numbers are assigned in this area. When calling from outside the U.S., the caller would dial the same way as if making a normal call to the United States. In most cases, international callers would dial the international access code followed by the U.S. county code (1) and then the K7 number. For the exact method of dialing, it is recommended that you contact your local telephone company. Since the K7 number is a U.S. number, the caller will incur normal international long distance charges.

Q: I am getting my faxes as voicemails. What causes this? back to questions Faxes should be sent during the initial greeting. If the sender waits until after the beep the K7 system will think they are sending a voicemail. You will have to educate the people sending faxes to you. We suggest changing your greeting to something like this, "You have reached the Unified Message box of John Doe. If you wish to send a fax, send it now. To leave a message, please speak at the beep."

Q: Why can't I open the attachments K7 sends to me?